

ANALYSIS OF REFORMS IN THE FINANCIAL AND TAX
SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the current work in the financial and tax system, government decisions and budget policies in Uzbekistan. The separate accounting of budget organizations and institutions and enterprises with a state share, as well as non-representation of extra-budgetary funds of ministries and agencies in the consolidated budget, hinders the full transparency of the State budget funds.*

Keywords. *Finance, tax, tax system, government, budget, budget policy, accounting, budget organizations, institutions, enterprises, agencies, budget funds.*

Today, the rapid development of all spheres of society and state life requires the implementation of reforms based on the improvement of public finance management, which ensures rapid and high-quality progress of our country on the way to becoming one of the leaders of world civilization.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy, reforms aimed at ensuring the stability of state finances are being consistently implemented in our country. In this regard, it is permissible to quote the following comments of the Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, "Further strengthening of macroeconomic stability and maintaining high rates of economic growth, including the balance of the State budget at all levels, the national currency and the price level in the domestic market are stable ensuring that it is our highest priority. In 2018, based

on the critical analysis of the current budget system according to the PEFA methodology, the results of the evaluation of the efficiency of public finance management, and the diagnostic evaluations of the openness of tax and budget policy based on the Transparency Code of the International Monetary Fund, the improvement of public finance management in the last two years a number of activities were carried out.

In particular, in order to ensure the openness and transparency of information about the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the State Budget) and citizens' participation in the budget process:

Since 2018, the information publication "Budget for Citizens" is being developed;

The "Openbudget.uz" information portal, where detailed information about the state budget is posted, was launched in January 2019;

Information on the implementation of the state budget is being posted on the website of the International Monetary Fund in accordance with the standards of the State Financial Statistics (GFS);

Starting from 2019, a mechanism was introduced to allocate at least 10% of the additional resources generated in the district and city budgets based on the activities reported by citizens;

Relevant norms have been included in the laws and by-laws, which regulate the full disclosure of the process of using budget funds on their official websites by those who dispose of budget funds and local state authorities.

Also, starting from 2020, based on advanced foreign experience, the draft State budget was adopted in the form of a law for the first time, and in order to increase the authority and responsibility of ministries and agencies, budget expenditures were approved not by sectors, but by ministries and agencies. At the same time, the practice of approving the expenses of the republican budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, and local budgets by the respective councils of people's deputies was introduced.

During 2018-2019, tax reforms were carried out in the country, the tax burden on the economy was reduced, the types of taxes were optimized, and the value added tax chain was created due to the increase in the number of value added tax payers.

In the new version of the Tax Code, the responsibility of the state tax service bodies for excessive collection of taxes has been strengthened, forms of tax control tested in foreign practice using modern methods have been introduced, and the procedures for calculating and paying taxes have been simplified.

At the same time, the results of the analysis showed that there is a lot of work to be done in the state finance management system in order to achieve the goals set for the planning of medium and long-term budget projects of the country. In particular, the separate accounting of budget organizations and institutions and enterprises with a state share, as well as non-representation of extra-budgetary funds of ministries and agencies in the consolidated budget, hinders the full transparency of the State budget funds.

A transparent methodology for calculating interbudgetary transfers that would allow for independent determination of local budgets has not been developed. It is required to improve the efficiency of public procurement and investment management, develop a public debt management strategy, and introduce an effective system of risk assessment to manage public assets and liabilities.

The indicated shortcomings and problems do not allow an objective and reliable assessment of the implemented budget policy and prevent effective analysis of budget expenditures with medium-term state programs.

In this regard, today it is necessary to carry out scientific research aimed at improving the health of state finances. Concepts of long-term development of the

country and priority state programs, in particular, the Development Strategy on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, the annual address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, the socio-economic development of the country until 2030 the concept of development and other similar state programs served as the basis for the development of the Strategy.

The main goal of the strategy is to conduct a well-thought-out budget policy, to increase the efficiency of the use of budget funds directed to the social and economic development of the country, and to create an effective system of public finance management aimed at ensuring their transparency and openness.

To achieve the goals of the strategy, it is necessary to implement the following main tasks:

- ❖ conducting a tax-budget policy directed at strategic goals and intended for the medium term;

- ❖ strengthening fiscal control, increasing the responsibility and accountability of the participants in the budget process by determining the limited amounts of budget funds allocated to first-level budget allocators by the Oliy Majlis;

- ❖ introduction of tax-budget policy aimed at ensuring long-term state financial stability;

- ❖ increasing the transparency of the budget process and the openness of budget information;

- ❖ radical reform of inter-budgetary relations, increasing the independence and responsibility of local budgets, and introducing a transparent mechanism for providing inter-budgetary transfers.

In the development of the strategy, the experience of not only economically developed countries, but also similar countries in terms of financial and economic structure was studied.

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